

Innovative Prosthodontic Solution: DMLS Metal Ceramic Restoration for Endodontically Treated Tooth - A Compelling Case Report

*Dr. Arpit Sikri¹, Dr. Jyotsana Sikri²

¹Associate Professor & Post Graduate Teacher, Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge and Oral Implantology, Bhojia Dental College & Hospital, Budh (Baddi), Teh. Baddi, Distt. Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India

²Associate Professor & Post Graduate Teacher, Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics, Bhojia Dental College & Hospital, Budh (Baddi), Teh. Baddi, Distt. Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India

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*Corresponding author: **Dr. Arpit Sikri**

Associate Professor & Post Graduate Teacher, Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge and Oral Implantology, Bhojia Dental College & Hospital, Budh (Baddi), Teh. Baddi, Distt. Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India

Abstract

Issues with endodontic procedures often arise due to inadequate coronal sealing or from subpar crown restorations. This can negatively impact the dental health and appearance over time. One popular restorative material known for its impressive strength is DMLS metal ceramic. Using the direct metal laser sintering (DMLS) technique for metal-ceramic crowns on the first molar post-endodontic treatment can result in pleasing cosmetic and functional results. DMLS is a method where a powerful laser binds metal powder particles together, layer upon layer, to form 3D items. This happens in a controlled setting, usually with inert gases, to avoid metal oxidation. This report aims to describe the process of applying DMLS PFM crown restorations to a first molar after endodontic therapy.

Keywords: 3D Printing, Additive manufacturing, DMLS PFM Crown Direct Metal Laser Sintering, Indirect Restoration.

INTRODUCTION

The best method for restoring teeth after endodontic procedures remains a debated topic. The final tooth restoration post-root canal is crucial for the treatment's success, as even minor leaks can reduce the root canal success rate by up to 40% [1]. Factors like the remaining tissue, its relation to neighboring teeth, and its interaction with opposing teeth influence the choice of restoration material and design.

Research has indicated differences between the dentin of endodontically treated teeth and healthy teeth [1–3]. While earlier beliefs suggested that endodontically treated teeth became brittle due to water loss [1] and reduced collagen connections [3], newer studies contradict this [4,5]. For instance, Huang et al. in 1991 found that neither dehydration nor endodontic treatment affected dentin's properties [4]. Sedgley and Messer also determined that treated teeth aren't necessarily more fragile [5].

Collectively, these studies suggest that fractures in treated teeth are more due to structural changes from the initial treatment rather than inherent dentin differences [6]. The process of accessing the tooth can weaken it, leading to fractures during use [7,8]. Also, many treated teeth have structure losses from caries or previous restorations. Research by Randow and Glantz highlighted the reduced protective feedback in treated teeth, which could increase fracture risks [9]. Thus, it's essential to use restorations that bolster the tooth's structure against mastication forces.

Tooth biomechanics are mainly altered by structural losses from factors like caries or treatments like endodontic access. A minor access preparation only slightly affects tooth stiffness, but canal treatments can further weaken it [10]. The most significant stiffness drop comes from more extensive preparations [11].

While traditional methods dominate Co-Cr alloy denture production, modern computer-aided techniques are gaining popularity [12]. Computer-aided design (CAD) and manufacturing (CAM) are widely used in dentistry, allowing for the

creation of various prosthetics [13]. Co-Cr items can be crafted using CNC milling or DMLS [14,15], which offer advantages over traditional methods. DMLS, an additive metal shaping technique, uses a powerful Yb-fiber optic laser to melt and fuse metal powder into precise layers [14,15]. This technology ensures accurate and durable denture creations [13,16].

This case report describes the method used for DMLS metal-ceramic crown restoration on a first molar post-endodontic treatment.

CASE REPORT

A 35-year-old woman visited the Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge, and Oral Implantology, complaining of discomfort around her lower left back tooth. She was then directed to the Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics where she underwent endodontic treatment for tooth 36 over several sessions. A month later, she returned to the Department of Prosthodontics, Crown & Bridge, and Oral Implantology for a follow-up.

The patient had no history of systemic conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular issues, or allergies. Additionally, her dental history was unremarkable. Radiographic evaluation revealed an endodontically treated tooth, specifically tooth 36.

Procedure

During the patient's first appointment, she received educational materials, guidance on dental hygiene, and was presented with informed consent documents. Subsequently, the root canal procedure was conducted over several visits.

For tooth preparation, a deep chamfer design was employed, which entailed removing 1 mm from the wall and 2 mm from the occlusal surface. The final subgingival preparation utilized a round-end taper fissure diamond bur. Following this, gingival retraction was carried out using a retraction cord (Roeko Stay-Put Retraction Cord, Coltene Whaledent Pvt. Ltd., Navi Mumbai, India) and a retraction solution (Dux GingiGEL, Kerr, California, United States) before proceeding to take the impression.

An impression of the maxillary teeth was made using condensation silicone (C-Silicone) Rubber Base Impression Material (Zetaplus Condensation Silicone Putty, Zhermack, Badia Polesine, Italy). Impressions of the mandibular teeth were also made using the same material and a two-step technique involving both putty and light body materials (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Maxillary & mandibular final impressions

The mandibular final impression is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Mandibular final impression

The maxillary master cast was created using type III dental stone (Gyprock Dental Stone Plaster, Gyprock India, Gujarat, India). In contrast, the mandibular master cast was formed using type IV dental stone (Gyprock Dental Die Stone Plaster, Gyprock India, Gujarat, India) as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Maxillary & mandibular master cast

During the tooth preparation, retentive grooves were incorporated due to the limited height of the abutment. These grooves served as additional retention features and were clearly visible on the master cast, as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Die preparation (Occlusal view)

A temporary crown, also known as a provisional restoration, was created using the indirect method (Protemp™ 4 Temporisation Material, 3M ESPE, 3M India, Karnataka, India). In the subsequent appointment, a metal try-in was conducted. Afterward, the shade for the crown was chosen using the shade guide, specifically shades 2M2 & 2M3. Following the trial fitting, the crown was sent to the laboratory for ceramic application and the final crown fabrication process, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Final DMLS metal ceramic (PFM) crown (Occlusal view)

During the next appointment, referred to as the bisque try-in stage, the objective was to evaluate the fixed crown's fit, check its occlusion, ensure proper articulation, and assess how well it integrated with the adjacent tissues. Figure 6 provides a glimpse of the DMLS metal ceramic crown.

Figure 6 – DMLS metal ceramic (PFM) crown

Following the bisque trial and the necessary occlusal adjustments, the DMLS metal ceramic crown underwent glazing in the laboratory. For the luting process, glass-ionomer cement (GC Fuji Gold Label Type 1 Luting Cement, GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) was used.

At a subsequent appointment, comprehensive evaluations were performed. Both the patient's feedback and clinical examinations indicated satisfaction with the treatment results. There were no complaints from the patient, and no negative responses were observed during percussion or palpation tests. The crown's condition was deemed satisfactory, with no signs of food retention or issues at the restoration margins. Additionally, the adjacent gingival tissues appeared healthy and normal, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Final DMLS PFM crown (in patient's mouth). a) Lateral view, b) Occlusal view

DISCUSSION

The term "success" in endodontic treatments is multifaceted. Clinically, a successful outcome means that the patient experiences no discomfort (is asymptomatic), and the treated teeth regain their full functionality. Achieving this relies on precise diagnosis, thorough disinfection, effective instrumentation, and detailed restoration processes that ensure both coronal and apical seals. Comprehensive management, as emphasized by Nurulaqmar-Iwani [17], highlights that faulty restorations are a significant factor leading to endodontic failures. Ineffective sealing at the crown or apex can allow microorganisms and toxins from the oral environment to enter the root canal, impacting the surrounding tissues. When choosing restorative solutions post-endodontic treatment, it's crucial to consider the specific requirements of each case and the amount of remaining tooth structure. Ideally, the selected restoration should provide protection for any missing occlusal surfaces or cusps. In the described case, the patient's past experiences with frequent restoration detachments highlighted the need for more durable solutions. The lifespan of restorations is influenced by multiple factors, such as the materials used, the techniques applied, patient factors, practitioner expertise, and local conditions. Studies have shown that indirect crown restorations have a 75-80% survival rate over a decade, while DMLS metal ceramic materials boast an impressive 88% success rate over 5 years [18 – 20].

For posterior teeth, a metal-ceramic crown was chosen due to its stability and cost-effectiveness. Leveraging the rapid manufacturing capabilities of DMLS, a Co-Cr metal framework was created. Laser sintering, a part of modern manufacturing techniques like rapid prototyping [21], has widespread applications in industries ranging from aerospace and defense to medical products, including a growing presence in dentistry. DMLS offers advantages like precision, simplicity, and sustainability over traditional manufacturing methods, often proving more economical [21]. Importantly, DMLS technology allows for the creation of fixed partial dentures with superior fit and mechanical properties [22, 23].

Although both Co-Cr and Ti alloy mixtures, made from fine powder, can be used to produce dental metal frameworks, the ease of fabrication and suitability make Co-Cr the preferred choice, especially when compared to porcelain restorations. Thus, for the posterior rehabilitation in this case, Co-Cr metal-ceramic fixed partial dentures produced via the DMLS method were deemed the best choice.

In the cementation process for this case, Glass Ionomer Cement (GIC) was chosen. This cement type was selected for its efficiency in the cementation process, its ability to prevent contamination, reduce potential errors, and minimize the overall chair time.

CONCLUSION

The application of DMLS metal ceramic crown restorations on the first molar following endodontic treatment results in aesthetically pleasing and clinically satisfactory results. These restorations not only provide effective sealing but also ensure precise marginal fit, thereby bolstering the success of the treatment. The post-treatment evaluations further validate this assertion, revealing no patient discomfort, negative reactions during clinical tests, and the absence of any issues related to the restoration margins or the adjacent gingival tissues. In this case, the integration of Laser sintering technology with a CNC unit was instrumental in achieving both functional excellence and aesthetic appeal. Furthermore, the patient continued with regular follow-up visits to monitor the durability and performance of the restorations.

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